

CLINICAL AND ECONOMIC EVALUATION OF POSSIBLE IMPLEMENTATION OF "PAY-FOR-PERFORMANCE" PROGRAM FOR PATIENT WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS IN BULGARIA

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Abstract

Introduction: The aim of this analysis is to assess the cost-effectiveness of the implementation of "pay-for-performance" (P4P) program to improve the control of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM), by having an acceptable glycemic control through pharmacotherapy.

Materials and methods: Patient-related health outcomes and saved direct medical costs by the NHIF in reducing the HbA1c level by 1% because of incentives under a P4P program were analyzed. A cost-benefit analysis was used to evaluate the cost-effectiveness of DM type 2 control. The final cost of pharmacotherapy was discounted with an annual discount factor of 3·5%.

Results: The cumulative discounted cost for intensified pharmacotherapy of DM type 2 for a ten-year follow-up period, is 6 425·63 BGN per patient. The effect of treatment, expressed in a reduction in the level of HbA1c by 1%, is related to savings from reduced diabetes-related complications (BGN 2 224·92 per patient). The calculated ACER values are below the threshold for favorable cost-effectiveness ($ACER = 14\,943\cdot32 \div 53\,546\cdot91$ BGN/% risk reduction). The result of adequate glycemic control stands out with the lowest value for ACER and the reduction in the risk of amputation or death from a microvascular event ($ACER = \$14\,943\cdot32/\%$ risk reduction).

Conclusion: The economic assessment provides cost-effective measures of the effect of treatment that can be included in the P4P program.

Keywords: diabetes, clinical evaluation, economic evaluation, P4P implementation, outcome-based payments.

Introduction

Diabetes is a growing health problem worldwide, mainly related to the development of micro- and macrovascular complications¹. According to the International Diabetes Federation, 463 million adults aged over 20 worldwide were diagnosed with diabetes in 2019. It is estimated that they will increase to 700·2 million by 2045, with one in every two persons suffering from diabetes remaining undiagnosed. The majority of them have type 2 diabetes². Diabetes affects around 426 000 people in Bulgaria, accounting for 7·9% of the population aged between 20 to 79 years (57% males and 43% women). Due to the burden of the disease, the cost of treating patients is about 10% of the total amount spent on healthcare worldwide. Age-standardized disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) were 801·5 per 100 000 people in 2019, a 27·6% increase from 1990.

To improve the quality of care for diabetic patients, many countries such as United States, United Kingdom, Australia, Taiwan, Ireland, and Italy are

launching P4P reimbursement programs for diabetes. These are payment models that provide financial incentives for achieving previously set health outcome goals as well as improved overall health care.

The aim of this analysis is to assess the cost-effectiveness of possible P4P implementation for the control of type 2 diabetes in Bulgaria, expressed in achieving adequate glycemic control through pharmacotherapy.

Materials and methods

Patient-related health outcomes and saved direct medical costs by the National Health Insurance Fund (NHIF) achieved through reducing the HbA1c level by 1% are analyzed. The median HbA1c in pharmacotherapy-treated patients was 7%. Adequate glycaemic control is expressed by lowering HbA1c levels and reducing the risk of diabetes-related complications.

The calculations reflect the payer perspective (theNHIF). A cost-benefit analysis was chosen for examining the cost-effectiveness of type 2 diabetic control. The final result is represented as an average cost-

effectiveness ratio (ACER). The time frame is in accordance with the evidence on health benefits in DM type 2 pharmacotherapy (UKPDS 35 observational study³). Thus, the chosen length of the time horizon is ten years.

Cost of pharmacotherapy

Annual expenditures on pharmacotherapy for a patient with DM type 2 are based on NHIF sales data for December 2021 - November 2022 (Table 1). To calculate them the following filters were used:

- ICD code – E11
- ATC code – A10 (medicines for the treatment of diabetes)
- INN
- ICD name
- Number of health-insured persons (HIP)
- Reimbursement cost (per month and year)

An average annual cost per patient is calculated using the published data on reimbursement cost and number of HIPs on a monthly basis.

Table 1.

Annual cost of pharmacotherapy of a patient with DM type 2

Year	Month	HIP Number	Cost of pharmacotherapy, BGN	Monthly average cost for HIP, BGN	Annual cost, BGN
2021	December	376 484	11 371 395·80	30·20	375·18
2022	January	381 323	11 567 723·26	30·34	
	February	365 001	10 873 560·33	29·79	
	March	387 866	11 899 839·40	30·68	
	April	382 331	11 732 520·68	30·69	
	May	383 561	11 882 948·37	30·98	
	June	381 663	11 965 603·58	31·35	
	July	380 943	12 042 596·18	31·61	
	August	387 436	12 466 487·42	32·18	
	September	384 539	12 411 516·92	32·28	
	October	387 428	12 538 187·22	32·36	
	November	390 901	12 791 677·01	32·72	

Abbreviations: HIP – health-insured person

Note: it is permissible for intensified therapy to be represented by a combination of two medicinal products. Regarding the single report of the HIP medicinal product packs, the annual number of patient-months is divided into two. Costs for medical devices are not included in the analysis.

Costs for medical activities

Since DM type 2 contributes to an increased risk of the number of complications (myocardial infarction, stroke or peripheral artery disease; diabetic retinopathy, nephropathy and polyneuropathy; heart failure in patients with other cardiovascular risk factors, and cardiovascular and overall mortality⁴⁻⁶), the assessment of the patient's pathway is presented by costing of medical

activities to control complications. The input expense data is in accordance with the National Framework Agreement for Medical Activities between the NHIF and the Bulgarian Medical Association for 2020 – 2022 (Contract No RD-NS-01-4-15 of November 23, 2022). Tables 2 and 3 provide the input data for the costs of medical activities.

Table 2.

Costs for medical activities for cerebral stroke control

Code	Nomenclature	Volume	Price, BGN	Share	Calculated cost, BGN
CP №050·1	Diagnosis and treatment of ischemic cerebral stroke without thrombolysis in persons over 18 years	37 940·00	1 404·00	91·82%	1 289·12
CP №051·1	Diagnosis and treatment of ischemic cerebral stroke with thrombolysis	968·00	3768·84	2·34%	88·29
CP №051·2	Diagnosis and treatment of ischemic cerebral stroke with interventional treatment	4·00	4034·96	0·01%	0·39
CP №052·1	Diagnosis and treatment of parenchymal cerebral hemorrhage in persons over 18 years	2 135·00	2268	5·17%	117·18
CP №053·1	Diagnosis and treatment of subarachnoid hemorrhage in persons over 18 years	274·00	2268	0·66%	15·04
Total		41 321·00	..	100%	1 510·03

CP №254	Prolonged treatment and early rehabilitation after the acute stage of ischemic and hemorrhagic cerebral stroke with residual health problems	13 788	86.4	..	7 days x 86.40 = 604.80*
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*According to expert opinion, seven days of rehabilitation are allowed, reported to the NHIF under CP No254
Abbreviations: CP – clinical pathway, OP – outpatient procedure.

Table 3.

Other costs for medical activities for control of complications of DM type 2

Code	Nomenclature	Volume	Price, BGN
CP №028	Diagnosis and treatment of acute coronary syndrome with persistent ST segment elevation, on interventional treatment	7 989	5 724.00
CP №255	Long-term treatment and early rehabilitation after myocardial infarction and after cardiac interventions	2 014	7 days x 85.02 = 595.14*
CP №029	Diagnosis and treatment of acute and exacerbated chronic heart failure without mechanical ventilation	66 000	1 004.40
CP №192	Surgical interventions in diabetic foot without vascular reconstructive operations	6 641	1 928.66
OP №19	Surgical removal of cataracts	45 000	507.60

*According to expert opinion, seven days of rehabilitation are allowed, reported to the NHIF under CP No255
Abbreviations: CP – clinical pathway, OP – outpatient procedure.

The final pharmacotherapy cost was discounted with an annual discount factor of 3.5%.

Input data on health benefits

The inputs for health benefits are the results of the UKPDS 35 observational study, which followed up patients with DM type 2 treated with insulin or other medicinal products versus a conventional treatment approach with diet.³ Over a follow-up period of ten years (median), patients on intensified insulin or other medicinal products reached an HbA1c level of 7% (median) versus 7.9% for patients on diet and exercise regimen. For patients with adequate glycemic control, a reduction in HbA1c level of 1% is associated with a risk re-

duction in stroke by 12%, heart failure by 16%, amputation or death from a microvascular event by 43%, myocardial infarction by 14% and cataract removal by 19%.

Results

The cumulative discounted cost for intensified pharmacotherapy of type 2 diabetes for a patient over a ten-year follow-up period is BGN 6 425.63. The effect of treatment, indicated as a 1% reduction in HbA1c, is related to savings from medical activities for diabetes-related complications (BGN 2 224.92 per patient, table 3).

Table 3.

Savings on direct medical costs

Complications	Medical activity to control complication	Risk reduction	Savings, BGN
Cataract removal	OP №19	19%	96.44
Stroke	CP №050.1 CP №051.1 CP №051.2 CP №052.1 CP №053.1 CP №254	12%	253.78
Heart failure	CP №029	16%	160.70
Amputation or death from a microvascular event	CP №192	43%	829.32
Myocardial infarction	CP №028, CP №255	14%	884.68
Total costs saved			2 224.92

Abbreviations: CP – clinical pathway, OP – outpatient procedure.

Using the data on pharmacotherapy costs and health benefits (reducing the risk of diabetes-related complications), a mean cost-effectiveness ratio of the administered treatment (with insulin or other medicinal products) was calculated. The conclusion on cost-effec-

tiveness is based on an estimated threshold for favorable cost-effectiveness of BGN 60 636·00 per unit of measurable health indicator (three times GDP per capita according to data from the National Statistical Institute for 2021). The results of the cost-outcome analysis are presented in Table 4.

Table 4.

Results of cost-benefit analysis

Complications	Risk reduction	Cumulative cost of pharmacotherapy, BGN	ACER, BGN./% Risk reduction
Reducing the risk of cataract removal	19%	6 425·63	33 819·10
Reducing the risk of stroke	12%		53 546·91
Reducing the risk of developing heart failure	16%		40 160·19
Reducing the risk of amputation or death from a microvascular event	43%		14 943·32
Reducing the risk of myocardial infarction	14%		45 897·36

Abbreviations: ACER – Average Cost Effectiveness Ratio

From the conducted economic analysis it can be summarized that the approach of adequate glycemic control through insulin or other medicinal products is a cost-effective option to reduce the risk of diabetes-related complications. The calculated ACER values are located below the threshold for favourable cost-effectiveness (ACER = 14 943·32÷53 546·91 BGN/% risk reduction). The lowest value for ACER is the result of adequate glycemic control and a reduction in the risk of amputation or death from a microvascular event (ACER = BGN 14 943·32 / % reduction in risk).

Discussion

This study investigates the cost-effectiveness of potential implementation of P4P program in the treatment of patients with DM type 2 in Bulgaria, as measured by sufficient glycemic control achieved through pharmacotherapy.

The diabetes epidemic puts great pressure on the economic systems of all countries around the world, including Bulgaria. One of the key issues that the health insurance system must face is controlling the burden of the disease, increasing disease control, and minimizing government resources. Monitoring diabetes is a necessary first step towards disease prevention and control, which is now recognised as an urgent priority.⁷

In 2019 the public funds for the treatment of DM in Bulgaria are equivalent to approximately BGN 550 million. While 20% of the costs are related to outpatient follow-up – examinations, outpatient tests, serum glucose tests and insulin pumps, the other 20% are given for medical products, as all modern pharmacotherapies are reimbursed. Most of the costs (60%) are utilized for hospitalizations and treatment of diabetes-related complications.

In Bulgaria, diabetic patients pay 2·5 times more for health care than people of the same age without diabetes.⁸ At the same time, the costs per patient related to the diagnosis and treatment of DM, increase from

610 to 779 BGN in patients under 18 years and from 660 to 702 BGN in patients over 18 years.⁸ Currently, DM occupies the third place in health costs after malignancies and cardiovascular diseases.⁹

Most of the costs of treating DM are related to the treatment of late complications that result from poor disease control. As a result, the investment in better control is compensated by a reduction in the number of complications and a reduction in their expenses accordingly. A Bulgarian study models and evaluates the long-term medical and economic benefits in improving the treatment of DM type 2. The study shows that the achievement of metabolic control goals postpones the manifestation of milder complications by up to four years and the severe complications of diabetes by three to four years. Life expectancy increases by three years and the total cost per patient decreases from BGN 2 483 to 2 908 BGN.¹¹

Another retrospective study of the National Diabetes Registry examines the quality of diabetes control and its financial impact in Bulgaria for 2012–2016. By attaining optimal control, the study demonstrates a noteworthy decrease in the likelihood of complications arising from diabetes, resulting in substantial cost savings of approximately BGN 20 million. This outcome serves to alleviate the strain on the healthcare system, relieving its financial burden.¹¹

The results of these studies demonstrate that improved treatment and control of diabetes delays the occurrence of complications and reduces the unfavorable impact of diabetes on quality of life and life expectancy, and reduces in the long term the overall diabetes-related costs paid by the healthcare system in Bulgaria.

One of the possible approaches for economic assessment of the application of P4P mechanisms in Bulgaria would be the experience gained in Taiwan. The following findings were shown in a study on the cost-benefit assessment of P4P mechanisms for accelerating

the treatment of type 2 diabetes: In phase one of the trial, the QALYs for P4P patients and patients without P4P were 2·08 and 1·99, respectively, and 2·08 and 2·02 in phase two. The average incremental cost of intervention per QALY is calculated to be 335 546 TWD\$ for phase one and 298 606 TWD\$ for phase two, which calculated against EUR at a rate of 0·031 EUR/TWD means 10 239·09 EUR for phase one and 9 111·87 EUR for phase two. The mean of total medical costs for the P4P mechanism for QALYs were calculated to be 602 167 TWD\$ in phase one and 661 163 TWD\$ in phase two. Recalculated in EUR this means EUR 18 374·93 in phase one and EUR 20 175·18 in phase two. The team reports that both P4P programs are cost-effective and the return of investment (ROI) is 1·8:1 in phase one and 2·0:1 in phase two. Analysis of Taiwan's ten years of experience and the growth of P4P mechanisms from "pay for participation" to "pay for performance" provides long-term cost-effective resource use and cost reductions in terms of ROI. ROI remains high whether or not incentives are obtained at intermediate outcomes as part of the process-oriented Taiwanese P4P mechanism.¹²

Conclusion

The economic assessment provides cost-effective measures for the effect of treatment to be included in the P4P models. Strict glycaemic control is expected to lead to a decrease in the incidence of micro- and macrovascular complications of diabetes, and accordingly, the cost of their control.

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